

Trauma Nurse

Concise Technical Report

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Complementary technical documentation for the published manuscript cited above.

Temporary Test Access

At the time of this report, *Trauma Nurse* is a mobile-oriented Flutter application temporarily made available as a browser-accessible test build through GitHub Pages.

Temporary access link: <https://silviocesar73.github.io/traumanurse/>

Test access: Users may create a test account in the application interface; no public demo credentials are distributed in this version.

This temporary browser-accessible build is intended for demonstration, documentation, academic dissemination, and technical evaluation using fictitious data.

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Document status

This technical report is a complementary material associated with the published manuscript cited on the cover page. It is not intended to reproduce the full theoretical discussion of the manuscript; instead, it documents the software structure, functional modules, clinical data organization, and current technical status of the application.

Version information

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Abstract

Trauma Nurse is a Flutter-based application designed to support neurological assessment and nursing care planning in traumatic brain injury contexts. The system integrates the Glasgow Coma Scale, the Glasgow Coma Scale–Pupils score, a nursing assessment module organized by selected Basic Human Needs, and a suggested care plan generated from clinical findings documented by the nurse. This technical report complements the published manuscript cited on the cover page by providing concise documentation of the application architecture, terminology structure, multilingual implementation, PDF output, educational use, and current development limitations. The current version is implemented as a trilingual Flutter application in Portuguese, English, and Spanish, with language selection before login and language-aligned interface strings, clinical data files, and PDF reports. For temporary review, this mobile-oriented application is being distributed as a Flutter Web build through GitHub Pages.

Keywords: traumatic brain injury; nursing process; Glasgow Coma Scale; GCS-P; ICNP; nursing care plan; clinical simulation; Flutter.

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1 Purpose and Scope of This Report

This report documents the technical structure and current implementation status of *Trauma Nurse*. It is intentionally concise and should be read as complementary material to the published manuscript cited on the cover page. The manuscript provides the broader scientific, theoretical, and methodological discussion; this report focuses on implementation details that could not be fully accommodated in the article format.

The specific purposes of this report are to:

- describe the main functional modules of the application;
- document the clinical data structure used for signs, symptoms, nursing diagnoses, outcomes, indicators, interventions, and actions/activities;
- summarize the trilingual architecture implemented for Portuguese, English, and Spanish;
- indicate potential uses in clinical education, simulation, and professional training;
- identify current limitations and planned development steps.

2 Application Overview

2.1 General Description

Trauma Nurse is a mobile-oriented nursing application focused on neurological assessment and nursing care planning for people with traumatic brain injury. The application supports the registration of patient identification data, structured Glasgow Coma Scale assessment, pupillary response, interpretation of GCS and GCS-P scores, selection of clinical findings, generation of suggested nursing care plans, and production of PDF reports.

The application does not replace the nurse’s clinical judgment. Its function is to organize documentation, support clinical reasoning, and provide structured outputs for educational or professional use.

2.2 Core Functional Modules

Table 1 summarizes the main functional modules currently implemented in the *Trauma Nurse* application.

Table 1: *Main functional modules of the Trauma Nurse application.*

Module	Description
Login and registration	User access, registration, password rules, and local session control.
Neurological assessment	Patient identification, GCS components, pupillary response, GCS/GCS-P calculation, and severity interpretation.
Nursing assessment	Selection of clinical findings organized by selected Basic Human Needs.
Care plan generation	Suggested diagnoses, related needs, expected outcomes, indicators, interventions, and actions/activities based on selected findings.
Saved results	Retrieval, visualization, deletion, and PDF export of saved assessments and care plans.
Multilingual interface	Portuguese, English, and Spanish interface packages selected before login.
PDF output	Language-aligned neurological assessment and suggested care plan report.

2.3 Clinical and Educational Rationale

The neurological assessment module is grounded in the Glasgow Coma Scale, originally proposed as a practical scale for assessing impaired consciousness (Teasdale & Jennett, 1974). The application also incorporates the GCS-P approach, which combines GCS score and pupillary response as an extended index of clinical severity in traumatic brain injury (Brennan et al., 2018).

The nursing care planning module responds to a documented need for better articulation of nursing diagnoses and interventions in trauma and traumatic brain injury care. Sallum and Sousa (2012) identified frequent nursing diagnoses among trauma victims in the first six hours after injury, including risk for infection, impaired skin integrity, acute pain, impaired comfort, and impaired tissue integrity. Cruz Neto et al. (2022) also highlighted hemodynamic monitoring, Glasgow assessment, and care plan updating as relevant components of the nursing process in traumatic brain injury, while pointing to gaps in the formulation of nursing diagnoses and interventions.

3 Technical and Multilingual Architecture

3.1 Software Stack

The application was implemented in Flutter/Dart to support cross-platform deployment. Although the present technical report uses a temporary Flutter Web build on GitHub Pages for access and review, the software was conceived primarily as a mobile application for Android and iOS, with the intended possibility of use without continuous internet access once deployed as a native app.

3.2 Technical Reproducibility and Project Structure

The information below is intended to support technical review and future maintenance without converting this report into a full installation manual. Table 2 presents the main technical reproducibility information currently documented for review and maintenance.

Table 2: *Technical reproducibility information to support review and maintenance.*

Item	Current documentation
Framework	Flutter/Dart cross-platform application.
Flutter version	3.44.0
Dart version	3.12.0
Temporary web build	Flutter Web build deployed for review through GitHub Pages.
Typical web build command	<code>flutter build web</code>
Core application code	Main Flutter source files in <code>lib/</code> , including screens, services, models, persistence, and PDF generation components.
Clinical data files	Language-specific JSON packages for Portuguese, English, and Spanish clinical content.
Interface strings	Language-specific interface packages for Portuguese, English, and Spanish.
Generated figures	Technical report figures stored in the <code>figures/</code> directory.

3.3 Single-App Trilingual Model

The current multilingual version follows a single-application model. It does not contain three separate applications. Instead, it uses one shared logic layer and separate language packages for interface strings and clinical data. Figure 1 summarizes the main workflow of the application and connects language selection, neurological assessment, nursing assessment, care planning, record management, and PDF output.

Figure 1: *Main workflow of Trauma Nurse, from language selection before login to neurological assessment, nursing assessment, care planning, record management and PDF output.*

The intended structure is summarized as follows:

- one shared Flutter application;
- one shared navigation and functional logic;
- three validated interface packages: Portuguese, English, and Spanish;
- three validated clinical data packages: Portuguese, English, and Spanish;
- language selection before login;
- interface, clinical data, and PDF output aligned with the selected language.

3.4 Language Selection and Persistence

The user selects the language on the login screen before authentication. The selected language updates the login interface immediately and is preserved for the subsequent application flow. The current implementation is designed so that the language selection controls interface strings, clinical JSON files, and PDF report labels. Figure 2 presents this multilingual architecture and highlights the separation between interface packages, clinical data packages, and synchronized outputs.

Figure 2: Multilingual architecture of Trauma Nurse, showing a single Flutter application connected to validated interface packages, language-specific clinical JSON packages, and synchronized outputs for screens, care plans and PDF reports.

The core class organization of the application is represented in Figure 3. This summarized UML class diagram focuses on the main persisted and manipulated data classes used to store neurological assessment data and nursing care plans. It is intentionally concise and does not represent all screens, services, controllers, or implementation classes.

Figure 3: Summarized UML class diagram of Trauma Nurse, showing the main persisted and manipulated data classes related to neurological assessment and nursing care planning.

4 Clinical Terminology and Data Structure

The clinical terminology layer was organized using nursing concepts compatible with standardized nursing language and the International Classification for Nursing Practice (ICNP). ICNP is recognized as a terminology for representing patient data and nursing clinical activity, supporting communication, documentation, decision-making, and policy development (World Health Organization, n.d.). Methodological studies using ICNP, such as Clares et al. (2022), support the structured construction of nursing diagnosis statements in specific clinical domains. The current clinical data package was prepared from the ICNP/CIPE v4 tables used in the project workflow, and the exact terminology source/version should remain explicitly documented in future public releases of the dataset. Table 3 summarizes the quantitative structure of the current Portuguese clinical data package.

Table 3: Summary of the current Portuguese clinical data package.

Clinical data element	Current count
Basic Human Need groups in the assessment file	12 groups
Nursing diagnoses in the diagnostic file	116 diagnoses
Primary expected outcomes	110 unique primary outcomes
Expected outcomes, including candidate outcomes	226 unique outcomes
Indicators	80 unique indicators
Intervention label	1 shared emergency/urgent care intervention label
Actions/activities	358 unique actions/activities
Clinical signs/symptoms linked to diagnoses	115 unique findings

The mapping between clinical findings and suggested nursing diagnoses is operationalized in the language-specific clinical JSON files used by the application. This report summarizes the quantitative structure of the current package rather than reproducing the full finding-diagnosis matrix, which would be too extensive for a concise technical report.

4.1 PDF Generation

The PDF report includes patient identification, GCS components, GCS/GCS-P synthesis, interpretation, clinical note, and suggested care plan. In the trilingual version, report headings, labels, observations, and clinical content are aligned with the language associated with the assessment or saved plan. Future releases should review whether additional metadata, such as application version, date/time of PDF generation, and professional identification fields, should be included in the exported report. Figure 4 summarizes the operational sequence from neurological assessment to suggested care-plan generation, record saving, and PDF output.

Figure 4: Sequence diagram of Trauma Nurse, showing the operational flow from neurological assessment to suggested care-plan generation, record saving, and PDF output.

5 Data Privacy and Security Considerations

The temporary browser-accessible version hosted through GitHub Pages is intended for demonstration, technical review, educational testing, simulation activities, and professional training. In the current implementation, the application does not store patient identification data, neurological assessment data, Glasgow Coma Scale scores, selected clinical findings, suggested care plans, or PDF reports on an external server controlled by the project team.

The information entered by the user during use of the application is processed only to support the immediate interaction with the system, including neurological assessment, care-plan generation, record visualization during use, and PDF report generation. The project team does not have access to the information entered by users in the GitHub Pages build.

Generated PDF files should be handled responsibly by the user, because they may contain patient identifiers or clinical information entered during use. When the application is used in classroom, simulation, demonstration, or training activities, the use of fictitious or simulated patient data remains recommended as good educational practice.

The current report does not claim institutional certification, integration with official electronic health record systems, or readiness for unsupervised clinical deployment. Before any routine institutional clinical use, the application would require local assessment of professional governance, workflow integration, PDF handling, documentation policies, auditability, and compliance with applicable data protection regulations, including the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD) when used in Brazil.

6 Educational, Simulation, and Practice Use

The application may be used in classroom teaching, skills laboratory activities, and simulation-based education. In trauma simulation scenarios, it can support nursing students or nurses in documenting neurological assessment and care planning after initial stabilization or during simulated transport, without replacing direct patient care or team communication.

Educational use and clinical limitation notice

Trauma Nurse is not a substitute for the nurse's clinical judgment, institutional protocols, emergency care guidelines, or validated electronic health record systems. In educational, simulation, and demonstration contexts, users should work with fictitious data. Any future clinical deployment would require institutional authorization, data protection review, and local adaptation.

This educational use is consistent with the role of simulation as a structured strategy for developing clinical reasoning, decision-making, and documentation skills. The Healthcare Simulation Standards of Best Practice emphasize purposeful design, clear objectives, and alignment between simulation activities and expected outcomes (INACSL Standards Committee, 2021). In this context, *Trauma Nurse* can function as a documentation and reasoning support tool within a scenario, rather than as an autonomous decision-maker.

Beyond teaching and simulation, the application may support future research on clinical reasoning and nursing documentation in urgent and emergency care. By structuring the pathway from neurological assessment to clinical findings and care-plan generation, it may help researchers investigate how nurses or students articulate protocol-based assessment with nursing-process-oriented clinical judgment.

Potential uses include:

- neurological assessment training using GCS and GCS-P;
- nursing process documentation exercises;
- care plan construction from selected clinical findings;
- simulation debriefing based on recorded assessment and care plan outputs;
- comparison of documentation across students or teams in educational settings.

In clinical practice, the application may also be explored as a prototype for structured nursing documentation in urgent and emergency trauma contexts. Its current status, however, remains educational and technical, requiring further validation and institutional adaptation before routine clinical deployment.

7 Current Status, Limitations, and Future Work

7.1 Current Status

At the time of this report, the application has a functional trilingual Flutter build temporarily available through the web for testing. The main implemented features include language selection before login, trilingual interface

packages, language-specific clinical data files, GCS/GCS-P calculation, care plan generation, record visualization during use, and PDF export.

The current GitHub Pages version should be understood as a temporary browser-accessible build for demonstration, testing, academic dissemination, and technical evaluation. As a static web deployment, it does not provide persistent project-controlled user authentication across sessions. This limitation is expected to be addressed in future native Android and iOS versions.

The approved research protocol included content validation with expert nurses and usability evaluation with clinical nurses. Usability evaluation with nursing students was not part of the approved scope of the present study. Because the application may be made available for educational use, future independent studies may evaluate its usability, educational impact, and simulation use with nursing students in different semesters, institutions, and learning contexts.

7.2 Current Limitations

The current version has the following limitations:

- the current browser-accessible GitHub Pages deployment is provisional and should not be interpreted as the intended final deployment model;
- because the GitHub Pages build is a temporary static web deployment, user registration and login data are not persistently stored across sessions in a project-controlled authentication system; this limitation is expected to be addressed in future Android and iOS versions;
- the application has not yet been distributed as native Android or iOS applications;

Suggestions, corrections, and improvement reports

Suggestions for improvement, clinical terminology corrections, language inconsistencies, usability issues, or technical problems may be sent to the responsible researcher:

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Reports and suggestions may inform future versions of the application and may also support new independent studies conducted by other researchers or institutions.

7.3 Future Work

Planned development steps include:

- accessibility review and usability refinements based on user feedback;
- preparation for Android and iOS versions;
- support for future independent studies in educational, simulation, and professional training contexts, including possible studies with nursing students by other researchers or institutions.

8 Conclusion

Trauma Nurse is a trilingual Flutter-based application that integrates neurological assessment, selected Basic Human Needs, structured clinical findings, nursing diagnoses, expected outcomes, indicators, interventions, and actions/activities into a single educational and technical tool. This report documents the application's current architecture and data organization without duplicating the broader theoretical discussion of the accepted manuscript. The current version demonstrates the feasibility of a single-app trilingual model in which interface, clinical data, and PDF output are aligned with the language selected before login.

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